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Fibrous-cystic osteitis in the end-stage renal disease

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Renal osteodystrophy is a heterogeneous group of metabolic bone diseases that accompanies progressive chronic kidney disease. Brown tumours (BTs), localized forms of fibrous-cystic osteitis, appear as single or multiple well-defined lesions of the bone and are considered as the most pathognomonic skeletal changes that accompany this disease (1.5–13%). Differential diagnosis of BTs includes several pathologies, mainly a giant cell tumour and also chondroma, fibrous dysplasia, bone cyst, osteosarcoma. We present a case of a 37-year-old female patient, with the end-stage renal disease from hypertensive nephrosclerosis that was treated by haemodialysis for 7 years. She developed a left hand and a left calf oedema with mobility impairment. Laboratory evaluation showed a severe form of secondary hyperparathyroidism. Radiographs revealed lytic lesions of the left second metacarpal and diaphysis of left fibula. Further workup with bone scintigraphy (using technetium 99m-diphosphonate) located other areas of osseous metabolic disease. Diffusely high accumulation of bone seeking agent was in the whole skeleton, especially skull (maxilla and mandible), both patella, ribs (left II, V, VI, VIII, IX), right ulna, both fibulas and metacarpal region of the left hand. After the ultrasound of the neck and parathyroid scintigraphy (99mTc-sestamibi), multigrain hyperplastic parathyroid glands were detected and the patient was sent to surgery (subtotal parathyroidectomy). The majority of patients with secondary hyperparathyroidism caused by chronic renal failure are successfully managed medically. In considerable number of patients with refractory symptoms, where palliative surgical treatment is necessary, correct diagnosis of complications is based on a combination of clinical, biochemical and imaging findings.

Key words: Osteitis Fibrosa Cystica; Kidney Failure, Chronic; Hyperparathyroidism, Secondary

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Electrochemical ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y generator as a possibility for stable supply of ⁹⁰Y

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In the recent past, there has been considerable interest in the use of therapeutic radiopharmaceuticals in Serbia, leading to active work towards development of therapeutic radiopharmaceuticals. ⁹⁰Y is an attractive radionuclide which has the possibility of being produced in generators, and which is avidly pursued at Laboratory for radioisotopes at the Vinča Institute. The difference between the electrochemical potentials of Y³⁺ and Sr²⁺ was exploited for separation of ⁹⁰Y from ⁹⁰Sr. The method is the electrochemical separation of ⁹⁰Y from ⁹⁰Sr. The cell with three electrodes was used. Working and counter electrode were platinum electrodes and the reference electrode was saturated calomel electrode. Two-step electrolysis was performed for ⁹⁰Y separation. Removal of oxygen from the solution was achieved by bubbling of argon before the electrolysis. Potential between working and calomel electrode was kept at -2.5 V. After the second electrolyses, deposited yttrium was leached from the platinum electrode with acetate buffer. The quality of separation was performed by using extraction paper chromatography with chromatography paper impregnated with 2-ethyl hexyl, 2-ethyl hexyl phosphonic acid (KSM-17). Paper strip (Whatman No1) was developed in saline. ⁹⁰Y activity of megabecquerel level was successfully separated from its parent ⁹⁰Sr. The efficiency of the ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y generator was above 96% of the theoretical value and represents good basis for further development of this generator. ⁹⁰Y remains at the beginning of the strip (Rf=0) while strontium was moved with the mobile phase (Rf=1), which confirmed the good quality of separation. Electrochemical separation method has a practical application for obtaining yttrium from ⁹⁰Sr/⁹⁰Y generator in routine nuclear medicine practice. Also, a satisfactory quality of the ⁹⁰Se/⁹⁰Y separation makes this product suitable for further use.

Key words: Yttrium Radioisotopes; Strontium Radioisotopes; Electrochemistry; Electrochemical Techniques; Nuclear Medicine; Chromatography, Paper; Electrolysis